

Supplementary figure 1. The four most abundant species in the dataset. A. *Varicorbula gibba* (Olivi, 1792), scale bar = 5mm. B. *Turritellinella tricarinata* (Brocchi, 1814), scale bar = 1 cm. C. *Kurtiella bidentata* (Montagu, 1803), scale bar = 1 mm. D. *Tritia varicosa* (W. Turton, 1825), scale bar = 1 mm.

Supplementary figure 2. Median DFs of bivalves along the cores in both regions decline in the late 20th century and later in both regions. Note distinct peaks of DFs in the mid-20th century in both regions.

Supplementary figure 3. Median DFs of gastropods along the cores in both regions. Abundance of gastropods in the Po prodelta (especially in core Po 3) was often below 20 individuals, the threshold for the calculation of DFs.

Supplementary figure 4. A. Vertical trend in drilling frequency of the total assemblage for the Panzano core. Points indicate the observed drilling frequencies, bars indicate 95% binomial confidence intervals, and the size of the point is scaled to the sample size at a given core level. Thin grey lines indicate randomly generated time series Monte Carlo simulations based on the observed first differences between successive levels in the core. The simulated time series represent non-directional random walks but because drilling frequencies are very low, any starting value is close to the reflective boundary of 0 and thus random walks tend to drift toward larger values. White lines represent the median and 25th and 75th quantiles of all random walks. Plot based on 10,000 iterations. Grey triangle indicates a timing of increased anthropogenic changes estimated independently [26-30]. B. Autocorrelation in DF for different lags with the highest positive autocorrelation observed for lag 1 (adjacent levels). C. Distribution of first differences (Δ_{DF}) generated in Monte Carlo simulations based on probabilities given by drilling frequencies at each level. The thicker grey line indicates prior distributions defined based on observed first differences and the thinner black thin line indicates the actual distribution generated in the serial Monte Carlo simulation. D. Difference in DF between the lower and upper parts of the core with boundary successively placed at different levels in the core. The difference is computed as the difference in means (ΔM) between the two core parts divided by the standard error (SM) (this is equivalent to the t statistic). The grey lines indicate means and 95% confidence intervals based on Monte Carlo simulations. The maximum deviation indicating the most likely transition from higher to lower DFs is indicated by an arrow (also marked on main panel 'A').

Supplementary figure 5. A. Vertical trend in drilling frequency of the total assemblage for the Po 3 core. Points indicate the observed drilling frequencies, bars indicate 95% binomial

confidence intervals, and the size of the point is scaled to the sample size at a given core level. Thin gray lines indicate randomly generated time series Monte Carlo simulations based on the observed first differences between successive levels in the core. The simulated time series represent non-directional random walks but because drilling frequencies are very low, any starting value is close to the reflective boundary of 0 and thus random walks tend to drift toward larger values. White lines represent the median and 25th and 75th quantiles of all random walks. Plot based on 10000 iterations. Gray triangle indicates a timing of increased anthropogenic changes estimated independently [26-30]. B. Autocorrelation in DF for different lags with the highest positive autocorrelation observed for lag 1 (adjacent levels). C. Distribution of first differences (Δ_{DF}) generated in Monte Carlo simulations based on probabilities given by drilling frequencies at each level. The thicker gray line indicates prior distributions defined based on observed first differences and the thinner black thin line indicates the actual distribution generated in the serial Monte Carlo simulation. D. Difference in DF between the lower and upper parts of the core with boundary successively placed at different levels in the core. The difference is computed as the difference in means (ΔM) between the two core parts divided by the standard error (SM) (this is equivalent to the t statistic). The gray lines indicate means and 95% confidence intervals based on Monte Carlo simulations. The maximum deviation indicating the most likely transition from higher to lower DFs is indicated by an arrow (also marked on main panel 'A').

Supplementary figure 6. A. Vertical trend in drilling frequency of the total assemblage for the Po 4 core. Points indicate the observed drilling frequencies, bars indicate 95% binomial confidence intervals, and the size of the point is scaled to the sample size at a given core level. Thin grey lines indicate randomly generated time series Monte Carlo simulations based on the observed first differences between successive levels in the core. The simulated time series represent non-directional random walks but because DFs are very low, any starting value is close to the reflective boundary of 0 and thus random walks tend to drift toward larger values. White lines represent the median and 25th and 75th quantiles of all random walks. Plot based on 10000 iterations. Grey triangle indicates a timing of increased anthropogenic changes estimated independently. B. Autocorrelation in DF for different lags with the highest positive autocorrelation observed for lag 1 (adjacent levels). C. Distribution of first differences (Δ_{DF}) generated in Monte Carlo simulations based on probabilities given by DFs at each level. The thicker gray line indicates prior distributions defined based on observed first differences and the thinner black thin line indicates the actual distribution generated in the serial Monte Carlo simulation. D. Difference in DF between the lower and upper parts of the core with boundary successively placed at different levels in the core. The difference is computed as the difference in means (ΔM) between the two core parts divided by

the standard error (SM) (this is equivalent to the t statistic). The grey lines indicate means and 95% confidence intervals based on Monte Carlo simulations. The maximum deviation indicating the most likely transition from higher to lower drilling frequencies is indicated by an arrow (also marked on main panel 'A').

Supplementary figure 7. Sampling distribution of Spearman rank correlation rho based on 10,000 Monte Carlo time series of the total assemblage, gastropods only, and bivalves only for the Panzano, Po3, and Po4 cores. Negative correlation indicates that DF decreases with core depth (i.e., DF increases upward toward the present) and positive correlation indicates that DF declines toward the present. Random walks generally tend to display negative rho values because the boundary condition imposed by 0% drilling frequency tends to generate random walks that increase upward in terms of drilling frequency. The grey arrow indicates the rho value observed for the actual data. The reported p-value was estimated as the proportion of extreme iterations (simulated rho \geq observed rho) out of the total number of iterations (n = 10000).

Supplementary figure 8. A. Vertical trend in drilling frequency of bivalves for the Panzano core. Points indicate the observed drilling frequencies, bars indicate 95% binomial confidence intervals, and the size of the point is scaled to the sample size at a given core level. Thin grey lines indicate randomly generated time series Monte Carlo simulations based on the observed first differences between successive levels in the core. The simulated time series represent non-directional random walks but because drilling frequencies are very low, any starting value is close to the reflective boundary of 0 and thus random walks tend to drift toward larger values. White lines represent the median and 25th and 75th quantiles of all random walks. Plot based on 10,000 iterations. Grey triangle indicates a timing of increased anthropogenic changes estimated independently [26-30]. B. Autocorrelation in DF for different lags with the highest positive autocorrelation observed for lag 1 (adjacent levels). C. Distribution of first differences (Δ_{DF}) generated in Monte Carlo simulations based on probabilities given by drilling frequencies at each level. The thicker grey line indicates prior distributions defined based on observed first differences and the thinner black thin line indicates the actual distribution generated in the serial Monte Carlo simulation. D. Difference in DF between the lower and upper parts of the core with boundary successively placed at different levels in the core. The difference is computed as the difference in means (ΔM) between the two core parts divided by the standard error (SM) (this is equivalent to the t statistic). The grey lines indicate means and 95% confidence intervals based on Monte Carlo simulations. The maximum deviation indicating the most likely transition from higher to lower DFs is indicated by an arrow (also marked on main panel 'A').

Supplementary figure 9. A. Vertical trend in drilling frequency of bivalves for the Po 3 core. Points indicate the observed drilling frequencies, bars indicate 95% binomial confidence intervals, and the size of the point is scaled to the sample size at a given core level. Thin gray lines indicate randomly generated time series Monte Carlo simulations based on the observed first differences between successive levels in the core. The simulated time series represent non-directional random walks but because drilling frequencies are very low, any starting value is close to the reflective boundary of 0 and thus random walks tend to drift toward larger values. White lines represent the median and 25th and 75th quantiles of all random walks. Plot based on 10000 iterations. Gray triangle indicates a timing of increased anthropogenic changes estimated independently [26-30]. B. Autocorrelation in DF for different lags with the highest positive autocorrelation observed for lag 1 (adjacent levels). C. Distribution of first differences (Δ_{DF}) generated in Monte Carlo simulations based on probabilities given by drilling frequencies at each level. The thicker gray line indicates prior distributions defined based on observed first differences and the thinner black thin line indicates the actual distribution generated in the serial Monte Carlo simulation. D. Difference in DF between the lower and upper parts of the core with boundary successively placed at different levels in the core. The difference is computed as the difference in means (ΔM) between the two core parts divided by the standard error (SM) (this is equivalent to the t statistic). The gray lines indicate means and 95% confidence intervals based on Monte Carlo simulations. The maximum deviation indicating the most likely transition from higher to lower DFs is indicated by an arrow (also marked on main panel 'A').

Supplementary figure 10. A. Vertical trend in drilling frequency of bivalves for the Po 4 core. Points indicate the observed drilling frequencies, bars indicate 95% binomial confidence intervals, and the size of the point is scaled to the sample size at a given core level. Thin grey lines indicate randomly generated time series Monte Carlo simulations based on the observed first differences between successive levels in the core. The simulated time series represent non-directional random walks but because DFs are very low, any starting value is close to the reflective boundary of 0 and thus random walks tend to drift toward larger values. White lines represent the median and 25th and 75th quantiles of all random walks. Plot based on 10000 iterations. Grey triangle indicates a timing of increased anthropogenic changes estimated independently. B. Autocorrelation in DF for different lags with the highest positive autocorrelation observed for lag 1 (adjacent levels). C. Distribution of first differences (Δ_{DF}) generated in Monte Carlo simulations based on probabilities given by DFs at each level. The thicker gray line indicates prior distributions defined based on observed first differences and the thinner black thin line indicates the actual distribution generated in the serial Monte Carlo

simulation. D. Difference in DF between the lower and upper parts of the core with boundary successively placed at different levels in the core. The difference is computed as the difference in means (ΔM) between the two core parts divided by the standard error (SM) (this is equivalent to the t statistic). The grey lines indicate means and 95% confidence intervals based on Monte Carlo simulations. The maximum deviation indicating the most likely transition from higher to lower drilling frequencies is indicated by an arrow (also marked on main panel 'A').

Supplementary figure 11. A. Vertical trend in drilling frequency of gastropods for the Panzano core. Points indicate the observed DFs, bars indicate 95% binomial confidence intervals, and the size of the point is scaled to the sample size at a given core level. Thin grey lines indicate randomly generated time series Monte Carlo simulations based on the observed first differences between successive levels in the core. The simulated time series represent non-directional random walks but because drilling frequencies are very low, any starting value is close to the reflective boundary of 0 and thus random walks tend to drift toward larger values. White lines represent the median and 25th and 75th quantiles of all random walks. Plot based on 10.000 iterations. Grey triangle indicates a timing of increased anthropogenic changes estimated independently [26-30]. B. Autocorrelation in DF for different lags with the highest positive autocorrelation observed for lag 1 (adjacent levels). C. Distribution of first differences (Δ_{DF}) generated in Monte Carlo simulations based on probabilities given by drilling frequencies at each level. The thicker grey line indicates prior distributions defined based on observed first differences and the thinner black thin line indicates the actual distribution generated in the serial Monte Carlo simulation. D. Difference in DF between the lower and upper parts of the core with boundary successively placed at different levels in the core. The difference is computed as the difference in means (ΔM) between the two core parts divided by the standard error (SM) (this is equivalent to the t statistic). The grey lines indicate means and 95% confidence intervals based on Monte Carlo simulations. The maximum deviation indicating the most likely transition from higher to lower DFs is indicated by an arrow (also marked on main panel 'A').

Supplementary figure 12. A. Vertical trend in DF of gastropods for the Po 4 core. Points indicate the observed drilling frequencies, bars indicate 95% binomial confidence intervals, and the size of the point is scaled to the sample size at a given core level. Thin grey lines indicate randomly generated time series Monte Carlo simulations based on the observed first differences between successive levels in the core. The simulated time series represent non-directional random walks but because DFs are very low, any starting value is close to the reflective boundary of 0 and thus random walks tend to drift toward larger values. White lines

represent the median and 25th and 75th quantiles of all random walks. Plot based on 10000 iterations. Grey triangle indicates a timing of increased anthropogenic changes estimated independently. B. Autocorrelation in DF for different lags with the highest positive autocorrelation observed for lag 1 (adjacent levels). C. Distribution of first differences (Δ_{DF}) generated in Monte Carlo simulations based on probabilities given by DFs at each level. The thicker gray line indicates prior distributions defined based on observed first differences and the thinner black thin line indicates the actual distribution generated in the serial Monte Carlo simulation. D. Difference in DF between the lower and upper parts of the core with boundary successively placed at different levels in the core. The difference is computed as the difference in means (ΔM) between the two core parts divided by the standard error (SM) (this is equivalent to the t statistic). The grey lines indicate means and 95% confidence intervals based on Monte Carlo simulations. The maximum deviation indicating the most likely transition from higher to lower drilling frequencies is indicated by an arrow (also marked on main panel 'A').

Supplementary figure 13. Relative abundance of predatory gastropods along the cores in both regions.

Supplementary figure 14. A. Median DFs of bivalves in time bins in both regions. B. Median DFs of gastropods in time bins in both regions.

Supplementary figure 15. Differences in community composition and DFs between the Po- and Isonzo prodelta, which are best expressed along NMDS1. Both regions show temporal trends of community composition and DFs, which are best expressed along NMDS2. Size of circles is proportional to DFs.

Supplementary table S1. Information about sediment cores in the Po delta and in the Isonzo delta used for this study.

Supplementary table S2. Number of individuals and the DF for molluscs, bivalves, gastropods and for the four most abundant species in each core increment.

Supplementary table S3. Number of samples with minimum 20 individuals in the four time bins for the total assemblage, bivalves and gastropods, and the four most abundant species in sediment cores of the Po Plain (PP), of the modern Po delta (Po3 and Po4) and of the Isonzo delta (Panzano).

Supplementary table S4. Results of Fisher's exact test for statistical differences between the two sample groups (pre-anthropogenic and post-anthropogenic) for the four most abundant species.